

D6.4 Report n°1 on the 'One Health' Summer School (Y2)

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Work Package 6 Task #	Task 6.3: 'One Health' Summer School
Lead Organising Institute	University of Surrey, UK
Lead School Organiser (LSO)	Dr Victor Del Rio Vilas
Local Organising Committee	Dr Victor Del Rio Vilas, Prof Roberto La Ragione, Dr Piyali Basu, Dr Jade Passey, Dr Dan Horton
Collaborating Organising Institutes	Wageningen BioVeterinary Research (WBVR), the Netherlands Public Health England (PHE), UK, Chatham House, UK
Collaborating Organisers	Prof Wim van der Poel (WBVR), Prof Dilys Morgan (PHE)
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Introduction

Summer schools are an important component of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), as they provide training opportunities for the next generation of scientists. The OHEJP summer schools will focus on major One Health themes including zoonoses, emerging diseases and antimicrobial resistance.

The OHEJP summer school aims to provide knowledge, skills and competencies regarding efficient solutions to the multifaceted infectious disease global challenges to human, animal and environmental health through cross-disciplinary research and education.

The summer schools provide opportunities for collaboration between OHEJP partners, stakeholders and researchers working in One Health outside of the consortium. These scientific, but also social interactions are an important goal and aspect of integration of the summer school and will contribute

to building a future consortium to support the sustainability of the OHEJP (WP7), and to extend the OHEJP outside the EU in alignment with the “Go Global” approach.

The OHEJP Summer School 2019 was organised by the University of Surrey in collaboration with Wageningen Bioveterinary Research, Chatham House and Public Health England. The event was hosted by University of Surrey, Guildford, and Chatham House, London in the UK in August 2019.

Theme and Overview

The overall theme of the Summer School was “Approaches towards One Health Operationalisation”. The programme delivered a comprehensive foundation to One Health basics, prediction approaches, analyses of integrated disease surveillance, outcomes research, risk management, and decision quality.

Aims and Objectives

The One Health concept recognises that human health is tightly connected to animals and the environment. Multiple reports have highlighted the need for ‘One Health’ interventions towards the delivery of better health outcomes across each of the health domains. In other words, One Health actions must contribute value over and above the status-quo traditionally characterised by isolated or domain-specific approaches.

However, One Health Operationalisation, or the identification of concrete actions to implement the One Health concept, remains a challenge. The mechanisms to support a value-driven and efficient One Health Operationalisation are at the centre of the summer school.

This summer school aimed to provide:

- 1) An understanding of the complexity of health challenges and how to use a One Health approach to address these.
- 2) Methods to identify, characterise, and quantify the drivers of value from One Health approaches across programmatic areas (e.g. prediction, detection) and stakeholders.
- 3) An ability to recognise the methods and operational approaches for effective preparedness and response to One Health threats.
- 4) An understanding of the application of robust monitoring and evaluation tools to implement One Health interventions.

Summer School speakers

A photograph and short biography can be found [here](#) on our website for each speaker. This page was updated regularly as each speaker was confirmed as part of the promotional strategy to increase awareness of the event.

Logistical arrangements

The OHEJP Summer School 2019 was organised by the University of Surrey in collaboration with Wageningen Bioveterinary Research and Public Health England. The two week contact time was hosted by University of Surrey, Guildford, and Chatham House, London in the UK from 19th-30th August 2019. During the registration process, the relevant personal data was collected, along with any dietary requirements, and permission to publish photographs taken and testimonials. All delegates were escorted throughout the summer school by two recruited senior ambassadors, including travel between the two sites. Train tickets were purchased beforehand for all delegates and provided in their registration packs to travel between the two sites. Delegates stayed at pre-arranged en-suite University accommodation for two weeks. Breakfast, lunch and two coffee breaks were provided every day. After the summer school, delegates from OHEJP consortium member institutes were reimbursed all travel costs and registration fees.

Promotional Campaign

The Promotional Campaign was managed by the OHEJP Communications Team.

A [‘Save the Date’](#) promotional flyer was created and validated with the summer school organizing team once the dates and venues had been confirmed. This was promoted and distributed through the following OHEJP channels: the OHEJP website, OHEJP Twitter and LinkedIn social media channels, email communication via the Work Package 6 Bulletin and OHEJP newsletters.

Once the details of the first version of the summer school programme had been confirmed and the registration process had been put in place, a detailed double-sided [flyer](#) was created and validated with the summer school organizing team. This flyer was disseminated on the OHEJP [website](#) and promoted on the OHEJP social media platforms- Twitter and LinkedIn. Furthermore, the application form was disseminated on the OHEJP social media platforms and through the One Health Commission who disseminated the flyer and registration form through their newsletter and Facebook page. The event was also advertised in the Consortium and External OHEJP newsletters. During the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) the Summer School flyer was disseminated in the delegate bags and on the Communication stand. It was also highlighted at the end of the ASM during a presentation by the Scientific Coordinator. Consortium members were informed of the event via email and were actively encouraged to increase awareness throughout their institutes. The OHEJP Communication Contact Person (CCP) network was also utilized to disseminate information about the Summer School.

In total, 130 applications were received, proving that the promotional campaign was very successful.

Applications and selection procedure

The 130 applicants for the Summer School were from a range of educational backgrounds, including veterinary, medicine, biomedical sciences, public health, food, economics and nursing. The selection procedure was influenced by this to ensure that the diversity contributed to the success of the Summer School because it would bring many different One Health perspectives and initiate collaborative discussions.

Educational Background

Applicants also had a range of educational levels, which was once again an important consideration because the Summer School aims to train the future One Health scientists. It was important to have a range of educational levels to stimulate discussions and collaborations between the delegates but also so that those at undergraduate level could learn from their peers with more experience. The majority of applicants had a master's degree or higher qualification.

Highest Educational Level

The 130 applications were screened against the following criteria to select the 20 delegates:

- Consortium members vs. Non- Consortium members
- Male vs. Female
- Experience
- Educational background
- Highest Education Level
- Area of expertise

Delegates

The Summer School hosted 20 delegates from 11 countries and from the institutes listed below.

The delegates belonged to a range of education levels and interdisciplinary backgrounds which brought a diverse pool of experience and knowledge in One Health to provide this opportunity of these unique multi-disciplinary and collaborative interactions.

The delegates profiles included veterinary surgeons, Doctor of Medicine, Epidemiologists, Early Career Researchers, post-doctoral researchers, institute researchers, MSc students, and finally PhD students in public health, animal health (zoonotic diseases), environmental health, antimicrobial resistance, biological sciences, veterinary medicine, nutrition, health economics, global one health, and wildlife ecology.

(* OHEJP Consortium Member; ** OHEJP Stakeholder)

1. France

- a. École supérieure du bois
 - b. Université de Tours
2. Spain
 - a. VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre-UCM*
3. United Kingdom
 - a. The Animal and Plant Health Agency*
 - b. University of Surrey (School of Veterinary Medicine) *
4. Norway
 - a. Norwegian Institute of Public Health*
5. Thailand
 - a. Kasetsart University (Faculty of Forestry)
 - b. Mae Fah Luang University (School of Health Sciences)
6. Italy
 - a. Italian National Institute of Health, Istituto Superiore di Sanità*
 - b. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) **
7. India
 - a. Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University
 - b. International livestock research institute (ILRI)
8. Poland
 - a. National Veterinary Research Institute*
9. Hungary
 - a. National Public Health Institute*
10. Switzerland
 - a. University of Geneva
11. Russia
 - a. Mari State University

Programme Structure

The Programme consisted of two weeks of pre-reading ahead of the summer school (see [e-learning](#)), followed by 2 weeks contact time hosted by the University of Surrey (Guildford) and Chatham House (London) in the UK. Each day there was a fully catered lunch with two coffee breaks.

Delegates presented their current or future One Health challenge in their professional setting. The idea was to identify colleagues (amongst delegates and lecturers) who can help address these challenges. The school was promoted not only as a learning opportunity, but also a very important networking opportunity.

Delegates also learned a number of technical and organisational skills that they were able to practice on a number of case studies. The programme delivered an introduction to One Health basics, prediction approaches, analyses of integrated disease surveillance, the economics and ethics of One Health research, application of the NEOH evaluation approach, outcomes research, risk assessment and management, and decision quality. The programme also included several sessions for challenges which included analyses on data collected, designing a study, etc.

Delegates had plenty of opportunities during and after the summer school to follow up with lecturers to seek relevant resources and advice. The pre-reading materials, and all course materials (with

permission) were uploaded onto the OHEJP website. These materials can be accessed by the delegates after the summer school at any time after the summer school. Delegates also had opportunities to communicate with the lecturers and other delegates through the website communication facilities.

The welcome drinks social event provided an opportunity to encourage introductions, networking and collaborative discussions amongst delegates, lecturers and organisers in a more informal setting on the first day (see Image 2, [photos](#)). On the final evening, a three-course social dinner was organised to celebrate the successes of the summer school including the new interdisciplinary collaborations across so many countries worldwide with experts in very different roles in the fields of human, animal and environmental health, the knowledge and skills learned, friendships, and finally the overall experience (see Image 3, [photos](#)). The success of the summer school is demonstrated by the testimonials received.

One Health EJP Summer School Programme Week 1

Date	Time	Session	Lecturer
Monday 19th August (Chatham House, Simulation Centre)	09.00-10.00	Welcome and course introduction	Victor Del Rio
	10.00-11.00	Introduction Global One Health	Wim Van der Poel
	11.00-12.00	Emerging zoonoses	Wim Van der Poel
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	One Health governance	Afifah Rahman-Shepherd
	14.00-15.00	International One Health framework	Elizabeth Mumford
	15.00-16.00	UK's Defra One Health science	Kathryn Callaghan
	16.00-17.00	Operationalisation frameworks (exercise)	Kathryn Callaghan & Elizabeth Mumford
	17.00-17.30	Challenges	Victor Del Rio
	18.00 onwards	Welcome Drinks at Chatham House	
Tuesday 20th August (Chatham House, Simulation Centre)	09.00-10.00	Spatial analysis for integrated surveillance (SAIS) of One Health	Andrew Lawson
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Spatial analysis for integrated surveillance (SAIS) of One Health	Andrew Lawson
	14.00-15.00		
	15.00-16.00		
	16.00-17.00		
17.00-17.30	Spatial analysis for integrated surveillance (SAIS) of One Health	Victor Del Rio	
Wednesday 21st August (Chatham House, Simulation Centre)	09.00-10.00	Spatial analysis for integrated surveillance (SAIS) of One Health	Andrew Lawson
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Enhancing One Health surveillance: the example of integrated surveillance for arbovirus infections in the countries of the Mediterranean Basin, Middle East and Black Sea	Maria Grazia Dente
	14.00-15.00	One Health in Action: The Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance group	Dilys Morgan
	15.00-16.00	One Health Risk Assessment: Chronic Wasting Disease	Dilys Morgan
16.00-17.00	Challenges	Victor Del Rio	
Thursday 22nd August (University of Surrey, Lecture Theatre B. See 'Lecture Theatre Block on campus map')	09.00-10.00	Rapid risk assessment: appraising evidence and communicating risk	Dilys Morgan/ Helen Roberts Dilys Morgan/ Helen Roberts
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-13.30	Roles and responsibility of UK agencies	Bengü Said
	13.30-14.00	Outbreaks and challenges: <i>Salmonella</i> in feeder mice and <i>Brucella suis</i> and raw pet food	Steve Wyllie
	14.00-14.30	Using evidence to inform policy: <i>C. ulcerans</i> and <i>M. bovis</i> incidence	Katherine Russell
	14.30- 17.00	Scenario work and feedback	Dilys Morgan, Helen Roberts, Bengü Said, Steve Wyllie, Andrew Frost, Katherine Russell
Friday 23rd August (University of Surrey,	09.00-10.00	One Health and AMR	Steve Wyllie
	10.00-11.00	<i>Salmonella</i> : investigation of linked outbreaks in sheep and humans	Steve Wyllie
	11.00-12.00	Introduction to evaluation of One Health	Barbara Haesler
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	The NEOH evaluation approach	Barbara Haesler
	14.00-15.00		Barbara Haesler

Lecture Theatre B)	15.00-16.00	Application of the NEOH evaluation approach (practical exercise)	
	16.00-17.00	Challenges	Victor Del Rio

One Health EJP Summer School Programme Week 2

Date	Time	Session	Lecturer
Monday 26th August (University of Surrey, 32MS01. See Rik Medlik Building on campus map)	09.00-10.00	Risk preferences in One Health	Arthur Attema
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Economics of One Health – the animal owner perspective	Henk Hogeveen
	14.00-15.00		
	15.00-16.00	Ethics of One Health	Marcel Verweij
16.00-17.00			
Tuesday 27th August (University of Surrey, 32MS01)	09.00-10.00	Systems thinking: the Use of Scenarios in a One Health Context	Kayla Strong
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Spatio-temporal dynamics of human infectious diseases and its interest for understanding animal disease transmission	Jean Francois Guegan
	14.00-15.00		
	15.00-16.00	Challenges	Victor Del Rio
16.00-17.00			
Wednesday 28th August (University of Surrey, 32MS01)	09.00-10.00	Outcomes Research in Animal Health and One Health	Francesca Contadini
	10.00-11.00	Introduction to outcomes research: a pharma perspective	David Bartram
	11.00-12.00	Sources of value for One Health Interventions (workshop)	David Bartram
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Defining the value proposition and beyond (Workshop)	David Bartram
	14.00-15.00	Introduction to outcomes research: the academic perspective	Natalia Cernicchiaro
	15.00-16.00	Application of epidemiological techniques to outcomes research in animal and public health	Natalia Cernicchiaro
	16.00-17.00	Challenges	Victor Del Rio
Thursday 29th August (University of Surrey, 32MS01)	09.00-10.00	Connecting data analysis and modelling: estimating parameters for infection dynamics	Mart de Jong
	10.00-11.00		
	11.00-12.00		
	12.00-13.00	Lunch	
	13.00-14.00	Practical: Running and understanding SIR-type models	Joaquin Prada
	14.00-15.00	Environment, diseases, and vulnerability	Gianni Lo Iacono
	15.00-16.00	Complex Network Surveillance & Systemic Value Portfolio Design	Matteo Convertino
	16.00-17.00	Complexity-Uncertainty-Sensitivity Ecosystem Mapping	Matteo Convertino
18.30 onwards	Summer School Dinner for Delegates at the Ivy, Guildford		
Friday 30th August (University of Surrey, 32MS01)	09.00-10.00	Health decision analysis with conflicting objectives	Gilberto Montibeller
	10.00-11.00	Health decision analysis under uncertainty	Gilberto Montibeller
	11.00-12.00	Health decision analysis in practice	Gilberto Montibeller
	12.00-13.00	Close of the One Health EJP Summer School	Victor Del Rio

E-learning component

All delegates were provided instructions to create a user account on the One Health EJP website to gain access and utilize the features of the private space of the website. A private group was setup called '[One Health EJP Summer School Delegates 2019](#)', to which all delegates were invited to join.

In this group, delegates had access to all pre-reading materials from the 25 speakers delivering the sessions. After the sessions had been delivered, if permission had been given from the authors, the lecture materials were uploaded into the group. This group will remain on the website for the duration of the programme and at least two years after the lifetime of the programme. Therefore, this material is available to the delegates after the summer school.

They also had access to all other information required before, during and after the summer school. This included the final Programme, campus map, key delegate information such as for catering and accommodation, instructions and schedule, train tickets, vouchers and expense claim forms.

Certificates of Attendance

The Communications Team provided electronic copies of the Certificates of Attendance to all delegates. The template can be found in [Annex 3](#).

Networking Social Events

Two social events were organised over the course of the summer school.

A 'Welcome Drinks' session was hosted by Chatham House at the end of the first day to provide the opportunity for delegates and speakers to introduce themselves in an informal and friendly setting.

At the end of the summer school, a three-course dinner was arranged in Guildford for all delegates to celebrate the achievements and progress made, the ideas generated and finally, the new professional working relationships and friendships made.

Testimonials

Permission to publish these testimonials was obtained. This was done during the registration process.

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

1. "The OHEJP Summer School has been a great experience and opportunity to learn new approaches related to One Health issues from sessions given by experienced lecturers, but also a good opportunity for knowledge exchange within a very diverse group of participants from different backgrounds and nationalities"
2. "It was a really amazing course. I met many Professors who were experts in One Health. I also very much appreciated Dr Victor Del Rio Vilas who always stimulated the class and summarized the thoughts and discussion at the end of each section. The delegate group was also wonderful and created very thought-provoking and interactive discussions. Moreover, I have almost 20 new friends from different countries and different backgrounds. Thank you very much for such an unforgettable school at University of Surrey, UK"
3. "I am very grateful for being selected as an OHEJP Summer School candidate. This really has been an exceptional experience for me. I met so many great people from different cultures and made some friends (personals and professionals) for life. I have learnt so much from the lecturers. It was an amazing opportunity to see beyond my scientific background and see One Health from a whole new different aspect. Thank you again!"
4. "The One Health Summer School clearly defined ways to implement the One Health System thinking to being about solutions and health challenges and public health threats. The University of Surrey has provided perfect ambience for the summer school, and the summer school organisers made our stay and study very comfortable. I am sure to practice some of the strategies that I learned when I go back to my country"
5. "The OHEJP Summer School provided me with an opportunity to share and learn about collaborative multidisciplinary One Health approach. It was an amazing experience knowing the perspective of different stakeholders in One Health Operationalisation. I am looking forward to utilizing this network and knowledge in my professional One Health project"
6. "Starting from the point of the first day to the end of the course, I got a much broader view of what One Health involves and what other scientists of similar and different fields are working

on. I strongly believe it was a great idea to organize this summer school and I am looking forward to 2020!”

7. “This OHEJP Summer School was a wonderful experience. I am very grateful to have been selected and to be a part of this ‘One Health’ international family. I met fantastic people, friends and colleagues from all over the world. I learned many new concepts and I will carry these teachings in my heart, not only in the scientific context, but also in the human one. I wish everyone to participate and to have such a fantastic experience as this summer school”
8. “Great experience full of knowledge and meeting new people. All the workshops taken during the lecturers were phenomenal. It was indeed a great opportunity to connect with and meet new people coming from different backgrounds pertaining to One Health. We were able to learn about best practices and new opportunities from people who were actually utilizing them”
9. “Fun and enriching two weeks surrounded by multicultural students and professionals. It has been interesting to share experience and knowledge with people from different countries and with different backgrounds. Profitable and well-organized lessons and speeches given by professors and health workers”
10. “The OHEJP Summer School is an amazing opportunity to connect with outstanding professionals from the galaxy of One Health. Being a One Health MSc student for the last year, the OHEJP helped me reflect on topics like policy, decision making and most importantly the value of and evaluation of One Health. Thank you for this exceptionally organised and structured opportunity”
11. “The One Health EJP Summer School has been an amazing experience. It has been a great opportunity to broaden my mind with critical thinking and learning how policy is implemented and how science contributes to One Health decisions. I’ve met some brilliant people from a wide range of backgrounds with experience and knowledge. I hope it will come in very useful in the future and in a career in One Health”
12. “The OHEJP Summer School provided me an opportunity to share and learn about the collaborative multidisciplinary One Health approach. It was an amazing experience knowing the perspective of different stakeholders on One Health Operationalisation. I am looking forward to utilising this network and knowledge in my professional One Health project”

Photos

Written permission must have been taken from all those in any photographs taken. This is usually done during the registration application process.

Image 2: On the final evening of the Summer School, the delegates had a meal at the Ivy, Guildford to celebrate the success of the Summer School.

Image 1: The delegates, organisers and student ambassadors outside of Chatham House on the first day of the Summer School.

Image 3: Day 1: The introduction and welcome talk from the Summer School organiser Dr Victor del Rio Villas at Chatham House.

Image 4: Summer School organiser Professor Wim van der Poel presents the history of the One Health concept.

Image 5: The delegates presented posters of their current research in sessions throughout the Summer School.

Image 6: On the final day, the Summer School delegates signed each others' bags in their own languages as a keepsake from the event.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. **Please complete both the Internal Events Survey and the table below as accurately as possible.**

This information has been uploaded onto the Internal Events Survey.

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Summer School		
Date:	19 th -30 th August 2019		
Place:	University of Surrey, Guildford, UK & Chatham House, London, UK		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Y	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Y	Pitch Event	
Training	Y	Trade Fair	
Social Media	Y	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	Y	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	40	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	2	Other	
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: “Save the Date” Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP Summer School 2019 Approaches towards One Health Operationalisation

Save the Date!

Date:

19th-30th August 2019

Location:

University of Surrey, Surrey, UK and Chatham House,
London, UK

Audience:

Bachelor's, Masters and PhD students, and researchers with
some experience in a health related field.

More details will be announced soon! For more information visit:
www.onehealthjp.eu/the-ohejp-summer-school

Find us on social media

@OneHealthEJP

One Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPSummerSchool19

Annex 2: Summer School Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP Summer School 2019 Approaches towards One Health Operationalisation

Date:

19th-30th August 2019

Location:

University of Surrey, Surrey, UK and Chatham House,
London, UK

Audience:

Bachelor's, Masters and PhD students, and researchers
with some experience in a health related field.

Aim of the Summer School:

The One Health concept recognises that human health is tightly connected to animals and the environment. Multiple reports have highlighted the need for 'One Health' interventions towards the delivery of better health outcomes across each of the health domains. In other words, One Health actions must contribute value over and above the status-quo traditionally characterised by isolated or domain-specific approaches. However, One Health operationalisation, or the identification of concrete actions to implement the One Health concept, remains a challenge. The mechanisms to support a value-driven and efficient One Health operationalisation are at the centre of the summer school.

This summer school aims to provide:

- 1) an understanding of the complexity of health challenges and how to use a One Health approach to address these.
- 2) ways to identify, characterise, and quantify the drivers of value from One Health approaches across programmatic areas (e.g. prediction, detection) and stakeholders.
- 3) an ability to recognise the methods and operational approaches for effective preparedness and response to One Health threats.
- 4) an understanding of the application of robust monitoring and evaluation tools to implement One Health interventions.

Students will learn a number of technical and organisational skills that they will be able to practice on a number of case studies. The programme will deliver an introduction to One Health basics, prediction approaches, analyses of integrated disease surveillance, outcomes research, risk management, and decision quality.

Participants:

Students and researchers from both within the One Health EJP consortium and external to the consortium are eligible to apply for the Summer School. Applicants should have some experience in a relevant health related field.

Registration:

Registration is open now! Visit www.onehealthejp.eu/the-ohejp-summer-school for more information.

Key Information

Pre-reading and online material will be available prior to the start of the Summer School.

The Summer School will take place at the University of Surrey, UK and at the Centre for Global Health Security at Chatham House in London, UK.

Two-week's accommodation will be provided on the University of Surrey main campus.

Registration Fee: €200

Annex 3: Certificate of Attendance template

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This certificate is presented to:

Name

For participating in the One Health European Joint Programme Summer School held on
19th- 30th August 2019 at Chatham House and the University of Surrey, UK.

“Approaches towards One Health Operationalisation”

PRESENTED BY:

Victor Del Rio Vilas
Summer School Coordinator

Roberto La Ragione
Work Package 6 Leader

Wim van der Poel
Work Package 6 Deputy

This Summer School is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.